

ARISING CONFLICTS AS A RESULT OF FAILURES IN ORGANIZING COMMUNICATION WITH CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *An old school aphorism says: "The hardest part of working with children is working with their parents." If each pedagogue, relying on his experience and skills, does not spare his pedagogical advice in eliminating the shortcomings made by parents in the organization of communication with children in the family, there will be no problems in the educational process of the student. This article presents ideas about the role of human qualities, noble desires, and values.*

Keywords: *parents, family, pedagogy, human qualities, noble desires, values, relationships, family environment, Eastern etiquette, mother, purity, intelligence, honesty, honor, modesty, kindness, loyalty and loyalty.*

In the **introduction** part of the article, an effort was made to show that all qualities are formed in the family, paying attention to the fact that the family is a sacred place for a person, the social foundation of the human society. The main purpose of family life is to restore the population by having children, to ensure the succession and continuity of ancestors with generations, and the historical development of humanity on earth.

Most of us are used to giving the same education to all children in the family. We know that children have different looks, different characteristics, ability or inability, difficult, restrained or active. It is precisely according to these aspects that the method of approaching children, communicating with them and educating them is determined. We must not forget the expediency of the choice.

The behavior of some parents with their children in the family can cause immoral behavior in children and adolescents. Parental attitudes based on anger in the family make children bored from home. Boredom and lack of recognition of the family environment lead to the failure of adaptation to the family environment in adolescents. As a result, the teenager likes the unhealthy street environment outside of the family. The street environment can sometimes have an immoral content. As a result, an opportunity is created for the origin of educational disorders in a teenager who falls into an environment of immoral behavior.

Sometimes, the fact that some parents kiss their children too much, caress them, do not speak harshly, and do not give advice can be the reason for the origin of unethical behavior. Commenting on the theoretical aspects of the article, in fact, the family is a place of education where the human qualities, virtues, and values formed in every person from early childhood are improved, and the values and spiritual heritage of the Uzbek people, which have been formed for thousands of years, are developed. "All human qualities, such as honesty, truthfulness, honor, modesty, kindness, hard work, are first of all formed in the family." The first school of a child's formation is considered to be a set of mutual relations between parents. "When we talk about the family, the image of the mother is formed before our eyes. The first factor that ensures the sanctity

of the family is the purity, intelligence, kindness, loyalty and loyalty of a mother, a woman. High-class values such as mutual respect, kindness, honesty, purity, hard work, and humanity, which are manifested in the relations of parents, become harmonious in their relations and create a ritual of mutual relations in the family. This social process in the family shows the young generation's ideas, views, concepts, worldviews about the material world, social life, and Eastern etiquette rules and the correct guidelines for their practical observance. The spiritual image of the young generation, their behavior and behavior are initially formed in the culture of family relations.

Valuable information can be found in the relics of ancient peoples, sacred religious sources, masterpieces of oral creativity of the Uzbek people, works of the great thinkers of the East, about the rules of etiquette, standards, and the expression of human qualities that are manifested in the family interpersonal relations of the peoples of the East, especially the Uzbek people. In the sources, the unimaginability of human life without a family, perfect child upbringing, the culture of couple and mutual relations in it, the ways of a happy and prosperous marriage, are described in the form of wisdom and advice with the help of life examples. A. Fitrat describes the social nature of discipline and writes in his work "Family or family management procedures": "The happiness and honor of every nation depends on the internal discipline and harmony of this nation. Peace and harmony rest on the discipline of the families of this nation. Where the family relationship is based on strong discipline, the country and the nation will be strong and orderly".

If we pay attention to the practical aspects of the article, it becomes clear by itself that the problems of family discipline determine its legal tasks. Due to the continuous commonality between family life and the development of society, family problems have been the focus of its progressive representatives in all periods of society's development. Family life is so important for the development of society and for the development of children that it cannot be neglected even for a second.

Republican psychologists have conducted a number of scientific researches to study the problems specific to Uzbek families. In these scientific works, a number of issues such as family-marriage relations, preparing young people for family life, national identity in Uzbek families, disputes and their important causes, divorces and their negative complications are comprehensively studied and analyzed.

Family relations ensure mental and spiritual maturity of children and bring about a unique activity in parents. In particular, due to the direct influence of children, the range of their interests and activities expands, their interactions become richer in content, a deeper understanding of the essence of real life, i.e., a state of planning their own life span in the form of children's maturity and future, occurs.

The educational importance of communication with children in the family, the ability of parents to actively communicate with their children is the key to their knowledge and learning in the process of education, and the creative nature of educational activities, which creates the best conditions for the formation of a child's personality, provides an acceptable emotional environment in education, including the removal of mental and psychological barriers. It is an important tool that prevents the occurrence and ensures proper management of socio-psychological processes in children.

"...education should start from the day of birth. "Who does education? Where is it made?" is a question. The first home education to this question is a mother's duty. If we give the answer that education of the second school and madrasa is the duty of the father, teacher,

tutor and the government." These words of Abdulla Avloni are as if they were said for today's education and training.

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